

ICT Literacy and Online Accesibility of Grade 5 and 6 Parents of Bagong Buhay Elementary School: A Basis for Proposed Training on Intensified Parental Support

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Abstract:- Philippine educational system drastically changes as COVID-19 pandemic affects thousands of people. To address the needs of the learners Department of Education came up with the different distance learning delivery modalities as part of the department's learning continuity plan. Modular and online distance learning require vital role of home facilitators which serve as a bridge of home and school to achieve educational success. In relation, teachers must ensure the status of parents' ICT skills and online accessibility as basis for proposed training on intensified parental support, which is the main objective of the study. To address the problem, an online and written survey was distributed to the 34 randomly selected Grade 5 and 6 parents of BBES. The results of the survey showed that Grade 5 and 6 parents of BBES lack of Microsoft skills which are very essential in assisting pupils in accomplishing learning tasks in online learning; and majority of parents need more skills to perform internet surfing which serve as an online platform in online distance learning. It is also revealed that the majority of parents have an access in internet connection and ICT equipment and gadgets despite that the geographical location is in urban place. From the results, teachers must conduct a basic ICT training to equip parents with enough ICT competencies and further provide intensified parental support to their children. Additionally, it is recommended to develop new alternative ways of delivering lessons since some of the students do not have access to stable internet connection. The development of modules and ICT related activities should also consider the context and situation of the learner and parents.

Keywords:- *ICT literacy, online accessibility, parental involvement*

I. INTRODUCTION

COVID 19 greatly change the economy, business, lifestyle and educational system. As the world authorities seek solution in this global health crisis, DepEd is also trying to cope up with the new normal set-up in schools. New normal education imposes challenges and great responsibilities to teachers, students and parents in modular and online distance learning modality. In this pandemic time, DepEd calls for parental support and involvement to ensure educational success of the learners. Parental involvement is necessary to intensify since it provide impacts to student academic performance. It is evidently seen that the more parental involvement, the more students are likely to become productive members of society as well as excel in academics[1]. Hence, it is necessary to intensify parental involvement for them to nurture their child's learning especially in dealing with ICT related learning tasks.

To prepare the students for the challenges of the 21st century workplace and community leadership, the integration of information technology into teaching and learning process becomes inevitable[2]. Teaching and learning process integrated ICT to foster dynamic, proactive and safe learning environment. Through the use of ICT in online learning, various learning opportunities and activities can be successfully conducted. Moreover, parents should possess ICT literacy in order to support the teaching and learning process. Without teachers' and parents' competency and mastery skills of ICT integration which is appropriate to their needs, ICT could not be put into good use for instructional delivery [3]. Parents should at least have a basic skill in Microsoft such as typing and editing of text, creating spreadsheet and formulas, opening and preparing slide presentation so that s/he could assist the children in doing specific learning task. Further, teachers and parents should have a range of different technical and communication skills which include using chat rooms, word processing skills, web page authoring and using various kinds of ICT tools such as File Transfer Protocol (FTP), compress and decompress of files, e.g., Win zip and so forth [4]. They should also have technical know-how in surfing internet since many applications have been used as online learning platforms. Parents who lack ICT literacy find it hard to assist and support their child's learning since online distance learning requires ICT literacy. Domino effect might

happen if parental support in accomplishing online learning task failed. Given these challenges, the researcher would like to assess parent's ICT literacy and online accessibility as basis for the proposed training on intensified parental support.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objective of the study is to assess ICT Literacy and Online Accessibility among Grade 5 and 6 parents of Bagong Buhay Elementary School for the school year 2020-2021. The result of research will serve as basis for proposed training on intensified parental support.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Descriptive survey method was used in assessing the ICT literacy and Online accessibility of the students for modular and online distance learning. Thirty-four (34) parents serve as a respondent, at ninety-five percent (95%) confidence level, and five percent (5%) margin of errors. The researcher used simple random sampling technique which is done thru "fishbowl" method wherein each individual has the same probability. Google form survey and self-made questionnaire were used to gather data, composing of three parts. Section A is the respondent profiles, section B is the online accessibility, and section C is the ICT Literacy of the respondents. On the other hand,

descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentage, mean and rank were used in the analysis of data. The online and written survey was conducted upon the consent of the concerned principal. After gathering of data, information were encoded and downloaded from data sheets for the tabulation, computation and graph, interpretations. Arithmetic mean, frequencies, ranking, and percentages were used to describe the ICT literacy and Online accessibility of the respondents using MS Excel formula.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Profiles of the Respondents

Table 1 shows that there were 17 parents from the Grade 5-Mahogany and 17 parents from Grade 6 Bakawan who serve as respondents out of sixty total population. Both grade level has the same size of sample which can reflect the accurate results of the overall population. It was shown that by gender on table 1, we have 28 female respondents and 6 male respondents. Meanwhile, table 2 shows the age of the respondents which covers significant age bracket from 25 to 55 years old. It has shown that parents age is well-distributed but it may not imply anything on the study but merely for the purpose of profiling. However, table 3 also reveals the distribution of respondents' educational attainment wherein majority finished secondary education.

Grade Level		
	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Grade 5-Mahogany	17	50%
Grade 6- Bakawan	17	50%
TOTAL	34	100%
Gender		
	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	6	17.6%
Female	28	82.4%
TOTAL	34	100%

Table 1: Grade Level and Gender Distribution of Respondents

Age		
	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age 25-30	8	23.5 %
Age 31-35	7	20.6%
Age 36- 40	6	17.7%
Age 41-45	5	14.7%
Age 46-50	5	14.7%
Age 51-55	3	8.8%
	34	100%

Table 2: Age Distribution of Respondents

Educational Attainment		
	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Elementary Graduate	2	5.9 %
High School Graduate	15	44.1%
College Graduate	12	35.3%
Vocational	5	14.7%
Total	34	100%

Table 3: Educational Attainment of Respondents

B. ICT Literacy

a) Microsoft Skills

Microsoft skills cover typing and editing text in Microsoft Word, entering data and creating formulas in Microsoft excel, operating and creating power point slides. Base from the self- assessment survey conducted, figure 1 shows 35.3% of the respondents have no experience of encoding and editing text in

Microsoft Word. This imply that respondents lack of skills in terms of utilizing Microsoft Word and supporting learning in various learning task. Respondents may find it difficult to open, create, save and modify documents which is necessary in some performance based assessment of their children.

Fig. 1: Percentages of MS Skills using Microsoft Word

However, figure 2 shows that 47.1 % of the respondents have basic skills of using Microsoft Excel. It implies that 16 respondents sometimes used excel in

entering data, creating formula and editing text in excel. They can assist their children in utilizing the excel in different learning task given by the teacher.

Fig. 2: Percentages of MS Skills using Microsoft Excel

It is evident in the figure 3 that almost half of the respondents has no experience and has beginner skills in using Microsoft PowerPoint. This implies that the 47.1 % of the respondents lack knowledge in using and creating PowerPoint. They have ability in creating slides, adding transitions and playing slide presentation but requires further

training to gain enough skills of supporting children’s learning. The results of the Microsoft skills should become one the basis of the teacher in developing the difficulty of ICT related learning tasks. This also implies that there is a need to develop training which will capacitate parents’ Microsoft skills.

Fig. 3: Percentages of MS Skills using Power Point

b) Internet Surfing

Aside from Microsoft Skills, respondents' internet literacy should also be assessed because ICT are integrated and essential in teaching and learning process. Figure 4 shows that 19 of 34 respondents have used or have knowledge on the Facebook and messenger application. They are aware of utilizing online learning platforms and they communicate

learning opportunities and challenges that the learners encountered. Parents are able to join in assigned Grade level group chats, create messages, send learning outputs in written and performance based assessment, send pictures, videos and evidence of learner's progress and etc. This implies that the respondents didn't need to have further intervention and assistance in utilizing Facebook and messenger.

Fig. 4: Frequencies on the Awareness of Respondents on Facebook and Messenger

Figure 5 displays the frequencies of respondents' awareness in terms Google as online learning Platform. It is shown that 50% of respondents have knowledgeable and use the Google. They are able to search information and watch tutorials videos if the learners needed additional

information. Respondents also can utilize websites, and download informative videos if needed. On the other hand, 3 respondents, which is very few, have not yet tried to visit the Google website and explore its functions.

Fig. 5: Frequencies on the Awareness of Respondents on Google

C. Online Accessibility

a) Internet Connectivity

Figure 6 shows the access to stable internet connection at home. 18 of 34 parents have stable internet connection which allow them to support

learners doing online learning activities. However, 16 parents encountered poor connectivity. This means that teachers should think learning tasks which could possibly engage learners with and without strong internet connectivity.

Fig. 6: Frequencies of Stable Internet Connectivity of the Respondents

b) ICT Equipment

Figure 4 depicts availability of computer and gadgets which can be used in online distance learning. From the responses gathered, all respondents answered

“YES” on the survey. It implies that parent’s ICT skills could be possible intensified through proper intervention such as capacity building on enhancing ICT Literacy.

Fig. 7: Percentages of Availability of ICT Equipment

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Majority of the Grade 5 and 6 parents lack Microsoft skills. Most of the respondents are not aware in utilizing the Microsoft Word, Excel and PowerPoint. Moreover, they possess internet literacy or internet skills like properly using YouTube, Facebook, Messenger and Google as an online learning platform to support child’s learning. In terms of online accessibility, majority of Grade 5 and 6 parents have access to ICT equipment but found it difficult to access to internet.

Based from the results, it is recommended that the teachers should conduct a training on developing Basic ICT skills of the Grade 5 and 6 parents. It is necessary to capacitate the home facilitators so that they can intensify the parental support given to their children. Moreover, the teachers should also retool and revisit the modules requiring learners to perform ICT related skills. Teachers should redesign and realign learning activities based on learners’ and parents’ context such as online accessibility and ICT literacy. Assessing and capacitating home facilitators (parents) will greatly contribute to the success of new normal education set up.

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